

A STUDY ON SCHOOL TIMETABLE OF GOVERNMENT PRIMARY SCHOOLS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BONGAIGAON AND CHIRANG DISTRICT, ASSAM (2019)

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ABSTRACT

School timetable are extremely important for a variety of reasons. They ensure that no teacher is scheduled for too many back-back classes or two classes at the same time. Teachers are given the opportunity to modify lesson plans during preparation periods and collaborates with their colleagues. The timetable allows the student to know exactly when a specific subject is scheduled. A well construct timetable establishes a neutral rhythm and routine, which can be comforting to teachers and students. In order to understand the concept of school timetable and how it is implemented successfully, we conduct a survey on three-government primary schools of Bongaigaon and Chirang districts of Assam, India.

KEYWORDS: *Education, School Pant, School Plan, School Timetable.*

INTRODUCTION

Literature Review:

1. "Educational management and administration" published by KumudeswarSarmah in Feb 2016, in which there were some very helpful points were there regarding the study of educational management and administration and in understanding their process and its system of work.
2. "Foundation of Education" published by Dr.Phunu Das Sarma in year June, 2014. In which many necessary information were there regarding education, school, etc for the study and understanding their work, process, types, system and many other facts.

Objectives:

1. To find out the process of management of school timetable.
 2. To study the present pattern of timetable in the field of government primary school.
 3. To find out the interests of the students in the various subjects.
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4. To study the institutional planning of government primary school in terms of managing timetable.

Methodology:

i) Use of questionnaire – a list of questions that are asked answered by many people. A questionnaire is used to collect information, facts about a particular subject.

In questionnaire, which contains 16 questions on the basis of adjectives of project study, some suggestions for each person had been put systematically. All the answers were given by the headmaster, all faculty member of the government primary school, which has been collected for the folder analysis of the object.

ii) Use of tables for each object and their data analysis.

iii) Use of present year government primary school timetable for the study.

Sample of the study:

Government primary schools of Bongaigaon and Chirang districts, Assam.

Total number of schools = 3.

Details of the schools:

a) **M.E. School, Chapaguri.** It was established in the year 1983. Its location is Chapaguri Part-1, Chirang, Assam, Pin- 783380.

It is a co-educational type of school. The medium of the instruction in this school is Assamese. In this school, classes are up-to 8 having 5 number of teachers. It has playground for sports and other co-curricular activities.

b) **M.V.School, Kalibari, Bidyaniketan.** This school was established in the year 1972. It is located at Chungapota, Bongaigaon, Assam, Pin- 783381.

It is a co-educational type of school. The medium of instruction is Bengali. It has classes up-to 5, having 8 number of teachers. This school has a playground for sports and other co-curricular activities.

c) **M.E. School, Baikhungaon.** This school was founded in the year 1986. It is located at Bartalowa, Chirang, Assam, Pin-783385.

It is a co-educational type of school. The medium of instruction is Assamese. It has classes up-to 8, having 7 number of teachers.

What is Education?

Etymologically the word education has been derived from the word latin education which comprises of two latin words 'e' means 'out of' and 'duco' which means 'to lead'. Thus, education means to draw out something and to put in something. This means, through education our inner capacities, potentialities, abilities are developed and come into light. According to some other educationist, education has been derived from two other words latin 'educare' and 'educere'. Educare means 'to raise' or 'to nourish' and 'educere' means to enhance, to develop, to improve.

Thus education, means art of developing and enhancing the cultivation of various child's physical, mental and moral powers. In this sense, education is considered as a process, not as a product.

Meaning of education is understood by Indian thinkers: Education in India, in Indian approach it becomes necessary to cover the spiritual area. Here, it is accepted as a part of betterment by education.

In Rigveda, education is that which makes a man self-reliant and selfless.

According to Kautilya, "education means training for the country and love for the nation".

Modern Indian thinkers regarded education from the practical point of view and the idealistic one which was given by eminent Indian thinkers.

Mahatma Gandhi says, by education I mean an all-round development drawing out of the best in child and man-body, mind and spirit.

According to Swami Vivekananda, education is the manifestation of divine perfection, already existing in man.

Tagore says, education makes one's life in harmony with all existence.

Meaning of education is understood by Western thinkers. Education in the West, educational training like every other branch of knowledge started in the philosophical deliberation of the ancient Greek philosophers. Here, it is mentioned by 'Plato'. He termed education as a lifelong process starting from the first years of childhood and lasting to the very end of the life.

According to 'Pestalozzi', education is the natural, harmonious and progressive development of man's innate powers.

According to 'Herbert', education is the development of good moral character.

According to 'Rosseau', education is the child's development from within.

In the other words of 'Aristotle', education is the creation of a sound mind in a sound body.

Education – a bipolar of process. As a bio bipolar process, education is a two-way process. Both educator and the educand influence each other. In it, both the teacher – taught are the active participants in the process of education. Here, a good personality of the teacher modifies the behaviour of the students in every sphere of life and activity. The teacher and the students in being the two poles interacting each other or making a cooperative effort in education.

Education – tripolar process. Education is a three-way process. It is known as three-dimensional process involving the interaction of the personality of the education on that of the

educand and in a social setting. It maintained that the whole environment of the individual becomes the source of education and education takes place in the society and society setting. John Dewey, has rightly says, an education proceeds by the participation of the individual in the social consciousness of the race. It involves the interplay of the educator, educand and the social environment.

It is the socially it is a society which will determine the aims, content, methods of teaching. The educator tries to modify the personality of the students in the light of the needs of the society. The teacher, the child and the society, these three are the focal point of education.

Forms of Education: Education is the process by which society deliberately transmitted accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another. In this widest sense, education indicates ways in which people learn skills and gain knowledge, information and understanding. Their general three forms of education – formal education, informal education and mom-formal education.

Formal Education – it is that kind of education which is undertaken in schools, colleges and universities. It is a system where education is provided the four walls of the classroom. It is consciously and deliberately planned activity which is undertaken for the modification of behaviour of the child and leading him out of darkness and ignorance and moving the light of knowledge in him. With the advancement of the technology, the need of the formal education has increased enormously. Formal education age– bound and time bound. The student has to take admission in the school or college at a particular age. There, he has to play, pay regular tuition fees. There is also a fixed timetable which the teacher as well as the students has to follow strictly. The school starts at a particular time and gets over at a particular time. There are uniforms for the students which are distributed by the school authority. Both the teacher and the student have to maintain strict discipline.

Characteristics of formal education – following characteristics are noteworthy for formal education;

- It observes strict discipline.

- It is a consciously and deliberately pre-planned and predetermined programme of activity. It is provided according to certain set rules and regulations.
- It follows various techniques and methodologies.
- Education organised by some agencies, say the government or private agencies.
- It is age bound and time bound.

Informal Education – informal education is the type of education which does not follow the usual rules, methods, techniques and discipline of formal education. It includes education one through informal communication and reading books. It is not pre-planned or predetermined but it is a spontaneous activity which is obtained from a wider environment as contrasting to the four walls of a classroom. Here, education is obtained by living with the other members of the community from press, library, literacy clubs, mass media like radio, TV, internet, audio and video cassettes and also from religious organisation. This education is obtained freely and spontaneously. Informal education starts from the birth of an individual and ends at the death of the person. It is obtained from the day-day life activities of an individual. In here, there is no rules and regulation or discipline is to be followed neither educational authority as any kind of control influence upon them. Characteristics of informal education – some major characteristics of informal education may be outlined below;

- It is does not have any definite place.
- It does not follow any definite methods or techniques of education.
- It is not pre-planned nor it has predetermined curriculum.
- There is no specialised agency to impart this type of education.
- It is free from any discipline, rules and regulations.

Non-Formal Education – with the modernisation of the world, it has become very necessary for everyone to be literate. Literacy is the key for success and development of any nation. A nation cannot progress with illiterate and unproductive people. Keeping in view the needs, interest and capabilities of people, a new system of education that is non-formal education is introduced. Non-formal education is imparted through open schools, open university, open learning, corresponding courses, summer institutes, portal tuitions etc. In non-formal education system, education flexibility is the keyword. In this, there is no rigidity regarding admission, curricular, place of institution, mode of institution and time, duration of instruction. According to the needs of the learner, non-formal education has a diversified and fixed curriculum. Since there are flexible points of entry and exit, re-entry and re-exit, so it is life long as this system of education is open for all concerned and there is no large age bar for the education.

Characteristics of non-formal Education – Fordhan, suggest that in the 1970s four characteristics came to be associated with non-formal education;

- Relevance of the needs of disadvantaged group.
- It enables individuals to refresh and update their knowledge.
- It has flexibility in organisation and methods, focus on clearly purposes.
- Concerned with a specific category so person.

Main functions and rules of Education:

a) General functions of education;

- Development of innate power,
- All-round development of personality,
- Control re-direction and submission of instincts,
- Character building and moral development,
- Inclusion of social values,
- Building of good and responsible citizens,
- Preparation for adult life.

b) Functions of education for individuals;

- Development of natural abilities,
- Development of personality,
- Achievement of self-sufficiency,
- Preparation for life,
- Satisfaction of needs,
- Making a child civilised,
- Character building,
- Modification of character,
- vocational efficiency,
- all round development of the individual.

I. Concept of School:

School is an institution that offers teaching, learning experiences in life and through life. John Dewey said that school should be regarded not as place for the preparation of life but life itself. The world school means an organised group of people pursuing defined studies and defined levels and receiving instruction from one or more teachers frequently with the addition of other employees and officers such as principal, various supervisory inspectors and staff of maintenance workers. The term school is derived from the Greek word 'Skhole' which means 'leisure'. [Schole' which means 'leisure'](#). In short, school are places for formal instruction. School is a place for learned intercourse and instructions, an institution for learning and educational establishment, a place for acquiring knowledge and mental training etc.

School – An assemblage of scholars. According to K.G. Saiyidain, the school is the centre of vigorous life. It is in direct intimate contact with the realities of the life, reflecting the best and worthiest of its features which are simple enough to appeal to the child. According to Ross, schools are institution devised by the civilised man for the purpose of aiding in the preparation of

the young for well adjustment efficient membership in society. According to Herold Rugg, thinks of school as an enterprise in living, both social and personal.

Characteristics Of School;

- School are institution that are setup by the society deliberately,
- Schools has a fixed points of entry and exit,
- School honours to a body of rules and regulations,
- There are certain well-defined objectives in any school education,
- It has a definite and limited period of being taught,
- School emphasises on strict discipline,
- There are fixed methods of teaching - lecture, demonstration, project, discussion, etc.

Functions of a school in modern society, school utmost importance. The following points by highlight why school is important;

1. Schools are asked to reconstruct the society – school is the nucleus of the society. School plays an important role in construction of society. The society has certain expectations from the school. The society can develop only with the help of school. The school imparts education to its members and the various aspects of social life and the development of society.
2. School as a better place of education than home – home is the first place of education for a child, but through schools, the child receives that type of quality education which is far better than home. In a school, a child comes into contact with the broad realities of life. Their outlook to a particular object gains wide perspective due to contact with various social elements like teachers, friends, etc.
3. Harmonious development of personality – school education helps a child in all-round development of his personality. It creates necessary educational environment in order to identify and develop child's native talents.
4. Production of educated citizens – the school has in the production of educated and intellectual citizens who will able to use their power of reasoning and faculties of mind in their daily activities. It produces citizens who are free from all sorts of superstitions, narrow feelings and orthodox practice. This educated group of citizens can shape the future of the society.
5. Connecting link between home and the World – school has a social organ serves as a connecting link between of home and influences of the outer world. School inculcates the feeling of brotherhood, fellow feelings, fraternity, equality, love among its many members and to become a citizen of the galaxy.

What is School Plan?

The school plan is a written statement on the educational philosophy of the school, it aims and how it proposes to achieve them. It deals with the total curriculum and with the organisation of the school's resources, including staff, space, facilities, equipment, time and finance. It includes the school's policies on a range of administrative and organisational issues. The school plan is a

written resource document which facilitates coordinated development with the entire school community. Some essential characteristics of school plant in India;

1. Curriculum adequacy – school plant must provide the facility is necessary for the efficient and effective accommodation of all the required phases on the curriculum, co-curricular and community activities. Modern school required more space for the organisation of a different co-curricular activities, for this large area is required.
2. Safety and wellbeing – school plant should provide comfort, healthful living and safety of peoples, teachers and all who will use its facilities. The site should have pleasing surrounding which gives children a safety and comfortable stay in the schools.
3. Inter-functional coordination – a school plan should possess the characteristics of inter-functional coordination. Each unit or portion of the plant should be planned with the respect of their mutual relationship.
4. Efficiency and utility – the school plant should be planned and assembled in a manner that will promote efficient school management, because the quality of the educational programme is intimately related to the school plan. The size of rooms, the number of doors, windows, ventilators etc, all must be determined not by fancy but by utility.
5. Beauty – the entire school plant should be bear cheerful, attractive and pleasant look. The surroundings of the school building should be attractive and must provide a stimulating environment.

The school plan is a composed assertion on the instructive way of thinking of the school, it points and how it proposes to accomplish them. It manages the absolute educational program and with the association of the school's assets, including staff, space, offices, hardware, time and money. It remembers the school's strategies for a scope of managerial and hierarchical issues. The school plan is a composed asset report which works with facilitated improvement with the whole school local area. A few fundamental qualities of school plant in India;

1. Curriculum ampleness - school plant should give the office is important to the proficient and viable convenience of the relative multitude of required stages on the educational program, co-curricular and local area exercises. Present day school required more space for the association of an alternate co-curricular exercises, for this huge region is required.
2. Safety and prosperity - school plant ought to give solace, energizing living and wellbeing of people groups, educators and all who will utilize its offices. The site ought to have satisfying encompassing which gives kids a wellbeing and agreeable stay in the schools.
3. Inter-utilitarian coordination - a school plan ought to have the qualities of between useful coordination. Every unit or piece of the plant ought to be arranged with the admiration of their shared relationship.
4. Efficiency and utility - the school plant ought to be arranged and gathered in a way that will advance productive school the board, on the grounds that the nature of the instructive program is personally connected with the school plan. The size of rooms, the quantity of entryways, windows, ventilators and so forth, all should be resolved not by extravagant but rather by utility.

5. Beauty - the whole school plant ought to be bear lively, appealing and lovely look. The environmental factors of the school building ought to be appealing and should give an invigorating climate.

What is the School Plant?

School planned is one of the major aspects of a school administration. It refers to the material provisions of the school. The school campus, buildings, playground, library, laboratories, classrooms, equipment, hostels, common room, canteen all these put together means the same thing what the school plant management stands for. The school plan is of great importance because of its impact on the educational process and programmes.

1. Type of school, we see firstly whether the school is girls or boys oriented or co-educational, rural or urban, secondary or senior secondary. We determine the nature of activities involved in the school accordingly special need of the school is to be taken into consideration while framing the timetable.
2. Department regulations, State Department of Education fixes lengths of the school year and its terms i.e., when an academic year starts and even the number of periods for each subject.
3. Amount of time available, timetable is framed keeping in view available time that is the length of the school year and total number of holidays.
4. Principle of justice while assigning work;
 - Special care has to be taken that each teacher is assigned those subjects who he or she feels his or her best qualified to teach,
 - He or she does not teach in more than two departments,
 - Teaching load for every teacher is about equal to diet of others.
5. Principle of variety, it has been seen experimentally that change of room, seat and posture usually is an antidote against weakness. It is applied on both students and teachers. Variety can be introduced in the following manner;
 - no subject except science practical should be kept for two consecutive periods,
 - if the subject is taught for two or three times a week, period should be follows at intervals,
 - the same teacher should not have two consecutive periods in the same class,
 - the physical training periods, science practical and drawing work allow a change,
 - the same class should not be set in the same room for the whole day.

What is the School Timetable?

Timetable of school is the mirror which reflects the entire programme of the school. It is methodically prepared for the routine work of the day. It indicates the work of the day of school such as of the classes, ending of the classes, time of launch break, time of the periods, the time of tutorials or seminar classes etc. It is a pre-planned scheme of work for the students and teachers of the school. A timetable is a secondary school clock which allows – shows the time work of the school.

Need and importance of the school timetable. It is the necessary means of working a school. Some of the needs and importance of school timetable may be enumerated as follows;

- Systematic work – it is very difficult to perform the school in an unplanned manner. Timetable is essential to such activities to work in a systematic manner such as which classes are to be fixed earlier and which had to be given later is managed by the timetable.
- Distribution of equal attention – when timetable is prepared, it gives equal attention to all subjects. It includes seminar work, field studies, project work and other subjects.
- Improvement of subject's learning – school timetable can help in the progress of all the subject equally accordingly to the needs of the students and teachers.
- Needs of the students – it is necessary to fulfil the needs and demands of the school subjects. Many timetables give more importance on English, maths, science subjects which require more classes.

Types of school timetable, a good timetable has to include various aspects of students and teacher's needs. Accordingly, such as timetable can be divided into different classes or types;

- Class timetable – it is prepared according to do different classes and sessions. It is considered that classes should not be affected which are to be prepared on the basis of classrooms. Sometimes, it may be difficult when a school does not have sufficient teachers or school's classroom.
- Teacher's timetable – the headmaster should take the initiative to distribute the distribution of the teacher's work according to the availability of the teachers.
- Games timetable – this kind of timetable is not found in all schools. However, the big schools have sufficient play grounds and games rooms.
- Co- curricular activities – such timetable is prepared at the beginning of the sessions under different teachers in charges.
- Consolidated timetable – it is prepared on the basis of the whole timetable of the entire classes school. The sum total of all classes timetable including daily work of teachers, student's classes, etc are related. This timetable is a guideline to the headmaster to know about the duties of the teachers and the classes of the teacher's students.
- Home work timetable – in some good schools such type of timetable is found where different home task, assignment etc are previously planned for every week. It is prepared on the basis of discussions.

Timetable gives a clear vision and comprehensive picture of school activities i.e., what work is being done during which period, where, by whom and when. It is complicated task because it is determined by a number of factors and conditions which change from place to place and from school to school. The following findings are the results of a good timetable.

Findings of the Study:➤ **Finding related to the objective number 1 from table no. 1.**

Table no. 1		
Sl. No.	Variables	Percentage of acceptance
1	Present timetable is well planned.	(YES) 100%
2	Use of all available resources for timetable.	(YES) 100%
3	Class interval of each class are same.	(YES) 100%

The existing or present government primary school timetable, the process of management of the school timetable or established or create with a well-planned systematic manner, as per the rules and regulations by the government. All the necessary information with the help of available resources were properly used, while management.

➤ **Finding related to the objective no. 2.**

Table no. 2		
Sl. No.	Variables	Percentage of acceptance
1	Present timetable as same as last year.	(NO) 100%
2	Timetable is flexible.	(YES) 100%
3	School timetable are systematic process.	(YES) 100%

From Table no. 2, it is shown that present government primary school timetable is not same as last year timetable. They are flexible and changes from time to time, whenever it requires to bring some changes. It has been proved that, timetable and its needs of activities, subjects, courses changes from time to time.

➤ **Finding related to the objective no. 3.**

Table no. 3		
Sl. No.	Variables	Percentage of acceptance
1	Timetable is critical.	(YES) 100%
2	Timetable also based on interest.	(YES) 100%
3	Students interests also taken seriously.	(YES) 100%

From Table no. 3, revealed the interest of the students in the subjects. It is shown that arts and other co-curricular activities or mostly like by students. Table no. 3, also shows that on the special needs or interest of the students, teachers cooperatively continued their classes for the fulfilment of student's needs.

➤ **Finding related to the objective no. 4.**

Table no. 4		
Sl. No.	Variables	Percentage of acceptance
1	Institutional planning is necessary.	(YES) 100%
2	All faculty members follow school	(YES) 100%

	timetable.	
3	Students follows properly these rules and regulations.	(YES) 100%

From table no. 4, it is found that there is a full cooperation with the present government primary school timetable by all faculty members and their students. It seems there is no argument, problems regarding managing, following the present government primary school timetable.

Tools and techniques used for data analysis for the study:

1. Tool used for the study – questionnaire a list of which contains 16 question and having some suggestion by different members of the school, it has been answered properly.
2. Technique used for analysis of the data collected. – With the help of questionnaire, all the necessary information and all facts collected by the faculty member of the schools.
3. Use of present year school timetable on government primary school.
4. Use of number of tables for findings.
5. Data interpretation – data interpretation refers to the implementation of procedure through which data is reviewed for the purpose of arriving at an inference. With the help of questionnaire, list of 16 questions based on project objectives. All necessary data and facts and information were collected, with the help of present year government primary school timetable which is allotted for all the government primary schools are same as per the rules and regulations conducted by the higher authorities.

Suggestions:

There are some suggestions some faculty members on the betterment of the government primary school timetable, they are as follows:

- a) More subjects should be included on the interest of students, which brings interest in them, motivate them in a positive way.
- b) More time should be provided for co-curricular activities like yoga, for student’s meditation, for their proper development in all round way.
- c) Special courses of classes should be conducted for the students to bring up their talents and they get motivated in a proper way.

Conclusion

The present study, reveals that the present year pattern of the school timetable of government primary schools are effective, interesting, systematically managed, well planned and accepted by all faculty members of the school in a cooperative way. It has been seen that, for making this process, all the administrative, management, staff members should work together, for making it more effective and the needs of students, their interest should be taken care of while creating or establishing, planning school timetable.

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